

1. Electron micrographs of the developing endosperm of a) Kinmaze and b) CM1787 (*esp2* mutant). Arrow denotes new type of protein bodies. Bar = 0.5 μ m.

Two types of protein bodies (PB) (PB-I and PB-II) were observed in the endosperm of Kinmaze, as reported by Tanaka et al (1980). In CM1787, although new types of PB and PB-II were observed, PB-I was absent. Many ribosomes were observed on the surface of the new type of PB (Fig. 1 b), suggesting that these PBs, such as PB-I, were derived from endoplasmic reticulum. Immunogold labeling (Fig. 2) showed that the glutelin precursors of *esp2* mutants were deposited in the new type of PB together with prolamin, suggesting that the presence of glutelin precursor in PB-I leads to the formation of the new PB type. In three other types of mutants, both PB-I and PB-II were observed; the new type of PB was not found. The localization of glutelin precursors in these mutants was examined. These observations indicate that the different mutations in the processing pathway of glutelin precursors can cause PB variations among mutants.

2. Electron micrographs of the developing endosperm of *esp2* mutant showing the specificities of a) anti-b subunit antibody and b) anti-13b prolamin polypeptide antibody for a new type of protein body (denoted by arrow). Bar = 0.5 μ m.

We conclude that these mutations are concerned with the genes controlling the processing of glutelin precursors. The study confirmed that *esp2* mutation can result in the deposition of 57-kD glutelin precursors in PB-I, and that *Esp2* is a gene controlling the proteins responsible for targeting glutelin precursors toward the protein vacuole.

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Molecular mapping of genes for F₁ pollen sterility in rice

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F₁ hybrid sterility, probably caused mainly by pollen sterility constrains the use of heterosis in the subspecific hybrid between indica (Hsein) and japonica (Keng). Zhang and Lu (1993) proposed that at least six loci are involved in controlling F₁ hybrid pollen sterility.

To map *S-c*, one of the F₁ pollen sterility genes, Taichung 65 (a japonica variety, denoted as E₁) and E₅, its isogenic F₁ pollen sterile line carrying this gene, were used as parents. E₅ was developed using indica variety Pehku as the donor. It was then backcrossed with E₁ for 11 generations. One hundred and four F₂ plants from E₅/E₁ were used for the segregation analysis.

Pollen fertility was 98.5% for E₁ and 98.6% for E₅; however, pollen fertility for F₁ plants from the cross E₁/E₅ was 53.2%. Segregation of fertile and sterile plants in the F₂ population from this cross fit well to a 1-1 ratio ($c^2=0$).

One hundred and seventy restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers were used to survey polymorphism between E₁ and E₅, and only three markers located on the same chromosome detected different RFLP patterns. The three positive markers (RG227, RG166, RG369A) were tightly linked to each other and were mapped on chromosome 3 (Causse et al 1994). Polymorphism was low between E₁ and E₅, which could be explained by the short length of introgressed segments in the isogenic line, because it was developed through repeated backcrossing.

The polymorphic RFLP markers were then used to survey the filters with DNA from 104 F₂ plants, and cosegregation of fertility and RFLP patterns were analyzed. The genetic distances between the *S-c* locus and markers RG227 and RG369 were 0.5 and 2.5 cM, respectively (see figure).

Location of the S-c gene on chromosome 3. Markers are on the right and map distances (in cM) are on the left.

F₂ Segregation Patterns for RFLP markers in the cross between E₁ and E₅.

Locus	j/j	j/i	i/i	χ^2 (1:2:1)
RG227	0	51	53	50.1
RG166	2	52	50	44.3
RG369	2	52	50	44.3

Distorted F₂ ratios were observed for the three RFLP markers in the cross (see table). The results suggest the use of the one-locus sporo-gametophytic model in explaining F₁ pollen sterility in cultivated rice (Zhang and Lu 1993).

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Chloroplast ribosomal protein genes encoded in rice nuclear genome

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Plant cells contain three distinct types of ribosomes that are found in the cytosol, mitochondria, and chloroplasts. Chloroplast ribosomes are structurally and

functionally very similar to eubacterial ribosomes, most likely reflecting their endosymbiotic origin. Several chloroplast ribosomal protein genes have been cloned and sequenced, mostly in dicotyledonous plants. Publication of complete nucleotide sequences of the rice chloroplast genome (Hiratsuka et al 1989) has allowed scientists to predict about two-thirds of the 55-60 chloroplast ribosomal proteins encoded in the nucleus. These nucleus-encoded chloroplast ribosomal proteins are synthesized on cytoplasmic 80S ribosomes as precursor polypeptides with a transit peptide sequence, which is cleaved off during transport into the organelle.

We isolated and sequence cDNA clones for nuclear-encoded genes *rpl13* and *rpl28*, which encode chloroplast ribosomal proteins L13 and L28, respectively, in rice. With poly(A)⁺-RNA isolated from green leaves of 10-d-old rice seedlings (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Nipponbare), cDNA libraries were constructed in λ ZAPII (Stratagene). Based on the highly conserved region among chloroplast ribosomal protein sequences reported in other plants, such as tobacco and spinach, the corresponding rice DNA fragments were amplified using reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction and used as probes. Nucleotide sequences of positive clones were determined using the dideoxy nucleotide chain termination method on double-stranded DNA templates.

The cDNA clone of *rpl13* consists of 1,076 nucleotides, including poly(A)₂₉ tail, and contains an open reading frame of 702 bp. The cDNA clone of *rpl28* consists of 781 nucleotides, including poly(A)₂₀ tail, and contains an open reading frame of 411 bp. Compared with sequences from spinach and tobacco, amino acid sequences deduced from cDNA sequences of *rpl13* and *rpl28* are more conserved in the mature peptide region, which is actually assembled into chloroplast ribosome. than in the transit peptide region. The mature L13 protein has 85 and 58% amino acid sequence identity with the counterparts of spinach (Phua et al 1989) and *Escherichia coli* (Isono et al 1985), respectively, in the homologous overlapping regions (see figure, region C). The amino acid identity of the mature

A schematic representation of local alignment of amino acid sequences of rp128. Predicted amino acid sequence of rice rp128 cDNA was aligned with the homologues of spinach and E. coli using MACAW algorithm (Lawrence et al 1993). Darker shade indicates sequence blocks with higher homology scores.

protein of L28 is 75 or 32% relative to tobacco (Yokoi and Sugiura 1992) and *E. coli* (Lee et al 1981). The mature L13 protein of rice contains 24 amino acid residues of N-terminal extension (see figure, region B), which is 16 residues shorter than that of spinach.

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